

Procrastination and Individual Study Method of Students with Specific Learning Difficulties [SpLDs] In Reading Comprehension

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ABSTRACT: Procrastination is mainly defined by cognitive factors and significantly affects the performance of students with specific learning difficulties [SpLDs]. The individual method of study seems to be influenced by other factors, such as cognitive-emotional abilities and learning motivation. The aim of the study was to investigate the relationship between procrastination and the individual method of study, with emphasis on the comprehension of academic texts using the pedagogical tool. The use is according with the principles of Targeted Individual Structured Differentiated integration program for teaching students with specific learning difficulties [TISDPfSpLDs]. The participants N=411 undergraduate students come from the departments of the School of Humanities and Cultural Studies of the University of Peloponnese [Kalamata] and from the departments of the Agricultural University of Athens [AUA]. The results showed that procrastination is part of the reading behaviors in reading comprehension with which students' [SpLDs] are familiar in their individual study method. The conclusions highlight the beneficial effects of training on metacognitive skills using the TISDPfSpLDs, because they help control emotional and academic procrastination.

KEYWORDS: Procrastination, individual study method, specific learning difficulties [SpLDs], students

INTRODUCTION

The procrastination of students is often another obstacle to the completion of their academic duties in academic studies. Students diagnosed with specific learning difficulties find it difficult to attend and prepare their courses in the conventional way. Procrastination is expected and results from the cognitive and emotional barriers they encounter and lead them to poor understanding, controlled by absences - physical presence in classes and less by autonomous academic motivation in the curriculum. In addition, academic procrastination, according to Solomon and Rothblum (1984) [1], "can be seen as a practice of avoiding and postponing academic tasks or delaying obligations related to study and completion of assignments and is often accompanied by discomfort." The relationship between procrastination and academic performance in a meta-analysis study [2] has been linked to personality and individual differences. According to this research, students find it difficult to distinguish procrastination from reduced performance in classes and refer to negative experienced emotions that answer the question "if they attended in person" the lectures and workshops of the semester courses [3] [4]. The investigation of the mediating role of emotion is highlighted in the research [5] of recording experiences with frustration, anxiety, shame towards their fellow students, guilt towards their parents and in some cases according to depression and suicidal tendencies. Furthermore, researchers [6] [7] correlate academic procrastination with cognitive factors and the decision to undertake academic work in courses. The multidimensional approach to aversion to assignments at all stages of personal projects is justified with statements "that they find the lessons dissuasive, unpleasant, difficult or painful and the demands exceed their capabilities" or abilities. In addition, psychological research has shown that procrastination arises due to reduced self-perception [8] [4] due to excessive worry about wrong choices and mistakes, the doubts they have about themselves. These correlate procrastination with authoritarian upbringing, maternal psychological control, and parental intervention role in shaping academic self-perception [6]. Also, according to motivation theories, the Self-Determination Theory (SDT) refers to the contribution of positive emotional experience to general well-being. Modern educational psychology points out that internal and external motivation can contribute to internal autonomous regulation and control of procrastination in the individual study method [9]. From the above, the relationship between self-regulated learning and academic procrastination is limited with regard to behaviors in students with specific learning disabilities [SpLDs] [10]. Literature research exhausts studies on emotional intelligence and academic motivation in undergraduate students without SpLDs [11]. The necessity of the present study arises with the central hypothesis of investigating the correlation of procrastination with the individual method of study in the comprehension of academic texts in Academic Studies. It also examines factors that change the behaviors of those who have difficulty understanding schedules, certain deadlines in academic obligations such as progress or the delivery of assignments during exam periods. It also studies factors such as the minimum basis for admission to the University [12] that prevent the students with SpLDs from studying, preparing in a

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timely, appropriate and systematic manner and acting at the last minute under pressure. This study tries to investigate the relationship between procrastination and the individual method of study according the principles of Targeted Individual Structured Differentiated integration program for teaching students with specific learning difficulties [TISDPfSpLDs] [13]. This study aims to identify challenges and obstacles in the reading comprehension in tertiary education and if and how could to overcome these. Students with specific learning difficulties SpLDs. In recent years, the number of students with specific learning difficulties SpLDs has increased. They carry diagnoses with dyslexia [14], attention deficit, hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) [15] and autism spectrum disorders (ASD) [12] [13] [16] when enrolled in tertiary education. The SpLDs is a generalized term, which refers to a heterogeneous group of problems related to the functioning of learning and understanding of speech, reading, writing and mathematics. These are inherent difficulties in the individual, considered to exist due to dysfunction of the Central Nervous System and manifest throughout his life [14]. Problems of self-regulation and behaviour, social perception and social interaction may coexist with SpLDs. Research for the diagnosis of dyslexia, reading and writing results in descriptions according to the variations observed from person to person, considering SLD as a primary condition without excluding their existence in multitalented people, pointing out the need for an interdisciplinary theoretical and practical approach. In Great Britain, the term "dyslexia" is used as a synonym for SpLDs, while in the United States the diagnosis is based on the American Psychiatric Association's (APA, the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, DSM) which serves as a universal authority for psychiatric diagnosis. According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5, 2013) [17], treatment proposals are checked, as well as reimbursement payments by medical care providers. SpLDs are referred to as follows: [a] reading disorder (dyslexia), [b] math disorder (dyscalculia), [c] disorder of written expression (dysgraphia), and [e] learning disorder not otherwise specified. This includes those cases in which the various diagnostic criteria are not met to such a clear extent that one of the first 3 categories applies. Performance in reading, math ability, writing skills – measured by individually administered weighted tests and controlled with significant deviations below expected, given the person's chronological age, measured intelligence, and age-appropriate education. These disorders, including ADHD and ASD, significantly interfere with school and academic performance or activities of daily living that require reading skills [14] [10] [11]. In addition, according to the European Manual of Classification of Mental and Behavioral Disorders (ICD-10) of the World Health Organization, SpLDs are classified as Specific Developmental Disorders of School Disorders Abilities with sub-categories [a] specific reading disorder, [b] specific hyphenation disorder, [c] specific numerical impairment, [d] mixed disorder of school abilities, [e] Other developmental disorders school competencies including ADHD and ASD and [f] unspecified developmental disorder of school abilities. At the Pedagogical Institute in Greece [1999, 2006, 2009], SpLDs were studied and reflected in the Experimental Curriculum for Specific learning difficulties (Dyslexia) [18] [19] [20] following the Framework Curriculum of Special Education (FCSE) [21], the Learning Readiness Activities and the Book for the Special Education Teacher. The Experimental Curriculum for Specific Learning Disabilities (Dyslexia) has included the following skill areas [a] perceptual, [b] mnemonic, [c] graphomotor skills, [d] reading, [e] numeracy and [f] skills in organizing reading behavior. This was used in the heteroobservations in Inclusion Education Units in the present research according to the protocols of the weekly individual sessions of special education (Drossinou Korea, & Kriti, 2022). The main topic of discussion in them was the recording of SpLDs, their relationship with procrastination and their treatment. Individual study method and metacognitive skills at the University. Metacognitive skills in students with SpLDs refer to perceiving, interpreting and becoming aware of the routines they follow when studying according the principles of Targeted Individual Structured Differentiated Integration Program for teaching students with Specific Learning Difficulties [TISDPfSpLDs]. The individual study method includes exercises to prioritize, detect and identify the priorities of attending classes in person or remotely or with absences. The recognition of emotions, the accurate determination of the emotional state for each course that the students with SpLDs decide to study includes exercises recording cognitive and social information. Moreover, metacognitive skills at the University include exercises of self-observation of reading behavior [22] [23] [24] as well as exercises to infer other people's thoughts and intentions about reading difficulties [25]. On this basis, the identification of possible negative emotions in reading self-esteem and whether it can affect self-reports of procrastination assessment is investigated. The surprisingly small number of studies that have empirically tested this hypothesis have not tested whether training in metacognitive skills in students with SpLDs demonstrates significant correlations with procrastination and individual study method in the real world. Since functional reading in reading comprehension is a basic knowledge in the academic curriculum at the University. Training in metacognitive skills supports the individual study method with exercises that help students with SpLDs to realize working memory, the individual memory space for each lesson as well as to calculate the concentration of attention on it. Reading comprehension and preparation of lessons for exams. The preparation of the courses for the examinations requires skills of organization and reading assessment of the capabilities of the students themselves, taking into account the time required to understand the texts taught, exercises, experiments, etc. The emotional availability for the lesson can be hindered by waking up in the morning and the inability of them to come to morning classes even when they are workshops and absences are taken. The comprehension of texts runs individually through the reader's readiness to understand scientific terminologies that for some students with SpLDs sound "as unknown language". The negotiation of SpLDs with the professors is part of the preparation of the courses for the exams that the Academic Courses have planned to study, but also part of the training of metacognitive skills.

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In it, they learn ways to negotiate, as to have more time during the exam, to transfer of date when two courses are examined on the same day and the ability to discuss questions in person into the time of the exam in a text that they find difficult to understand. In the oral case, they inform the professors following their attendance with physical presence in the lessons, while in the written one, they send a short email to each professor separately, reminding them of their difficulties and attaching the student facilitate exams document with the possibility to take more time.

Image 1. Individual study method and metacognitive skills at the University.

Figure 1. Individual study method and metacognitive skills at the University.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This research uses a quantitative and qualitative descriptive method, because this will describe the current situation to the Universities observing the procrastination and individual study method of students with specific learning difficulties [SpLDs]. The type of research carried out based on its type is included in case study research in reading comprehension systematically, so conclusions are drawn through analyzing questionnaires and interviews obtained from respondents. So, the procrastination was studied in N=411 undergraduate students. Of these, N = 351 come from [N = 165, Department of Philology, N = 118, Department of History, N = 68, Department of Archaeology come from the University of Peloponnese and N = 60 come from the departments of the Agricultural University of Athens [AUA]. Each participant completed ten electronic questionnaires containing the main points of the courses they attended in the framework of the academic curriculum in the classroom at the end of the course in the presence of the instructor. Students from AUA with certified with SpLDs completed ten electronic questionnaires with content from the mnemonic techniques laboratories. Of these, N=40 was diagnosed and were supported with individual special education sessions on a weekly basis for ten months with the pedagogical tool applying the principles of Targeted Individual Structured Differentiated Integration Program for teaching students with Specific Learning Difficulties [TISDPfSpLDs] in the University [3] [3] [23]. The services were developed within the framework of the Act "Support of Social Welfare Interventions [26] for Students of the Agricultural University of Athens", with MIS Code 5045556 which has been included in the Operational Program "Human Resources Development, Education and Lifelong Learning". The data from the questionnaires were collected via google and ranked based on fundamental thematic analysis. These included the number of courses participating in the individual method of study of SpLDs, distinguishing laboratory from theoretical courses, marking [e] the laboratory and [i] the theory. In addition, the fundamental analytical method used in this study is an interactive model by Miles & Huberman [27]. In the fundamental analysis of the factors associated with procrastination is carried out continuously until the data is considered saturated. This analysis consists of data collection, data reduction, data presentation and drawing conclusions. The data collection with the fundamental analysis be carried out simultaneously with the process of collecting and writing findings from the examination date, the time of the examination, the examination area such as a certain auditorium, a certain laboratory room were studied. Also, used the data reduction, according to the data is focused on the fundamental main findings according to the students' statements were recorded with the assessment of the degree of procrastination [from 1 to 5] with the basic criterion of attending classes. The statements with feelings about study preparation and assessments if it is [i], positive, negative, indifferent or emotionally disoriented. In addition, the degree of study preparation was entered [1-10] in response to the question "if tomorrow you had exams with what you have attended, how ready do you think you are?".

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[a] Faculty of Humanities and Cultural Studies					
Departments	Lesson	Participating students with or without SpLDs	Successful apomic study method	Unsuccessful individual study method	Procrastination
department of archeology and Cultural Studies	12I/ΠA-1_18 - Pedagogy of School Integration for students with Special Educational Needs	11 students with SpLDs from 118	35	25	58
department of history and Cultural Studies	12A/PDI-1_18 - Pedagogy of School Integration for students with Special Educational Needs	16 students with SpLDs from 68	32	12	24
Department of Philology	13565_14 - Pedagogy of school integration of students with special educational needs	16 students with SpLDs from 62	23	7	32
Department of Philology	13643_11 - Special Education and Training	10 students with SpLDs from 103	66	5	32
		133 students with SpLDs from 351	156	49	146

Figure 2. Data from the departments of the School of Humanities and Cultural Studies of the University of Peloponnese [Kalamata]

Presentation of qualitative data is presented in narrative form which explains the relationship between the procrastination and individual study method of students with specific learning difficulties [SpLDs]. So, the factors for procrastination included student statements estimating the degree of concentration of attention from 1 to 10 as well as mentioning ways to facilitate written exams indicating whether they are progressions [1], group work [2], individual work [3], multiple choices [4], topic development [5]-and the portfolio [6] alongside orality.

[3] Agricultural University of Athens					
		Our Fine participants	Successful individual study method	Unsuccessful individual study method	Procrastination
Department of Plant Science Production- SCHOOL OF PLANT SCIENCES Department of Biotechnology	[10] Workshops of mnemonic techniques	16	6	4	6
School of Applied Biology and Biotechnology	[10] Workshops of mnemonic techniques	10	5	2	3
Department of Agriculture Economy and Development School of Applied Economics and Social Sciences Scientist	[10] Workshops of mnemonic techniques	8	2	2	4
Department of Food Science and Human Nutrition - School of Food Science and Nutrition	[10] Workshops of mnemonic techniques	4	2	1	1
Department of Natural Resource Utilization and Agricultural Engineering SCHOOL OF ENVIRONMENTAL & AGRICULTURAL ENGINEERING	[10] Workshops of mnemonic techniques	5	2	1	1
Department of Animal Production Science - SCHOOL OF ANIMAL SCIENCES	[10] Workshops of mnemonic techniques	17	8	4	5
		60	26	14	20

Figure 3. Data from the departments of the Agricultural University of Athens [AUA].

The limitations

The limitations of this research refer to the different procedures for meeting and supporting students with SpLDs and assessing the degree of procrastination they declare [28]. In the Peloponnese, most of the process was developed in the courses of thirteen lectures for each semester, giving precedence to students without SpLDs. As part of the activities of the academic student advisor, the issue of procrastination was discussed individually with those students who voluntarily took part in the educational program of metacognitive skills. Even at the end of the semester, some students with SpLDs sent the diagnoses or the decision of the department to be examined orally. In Athens, the process was described in the factsheet and was part of the deliverables. Thus, the discussion with metacognitive skills exercises for the individual study method with emphasis on reading comprehension was discussed in individual sessions of Special Education and Training [SET] and mnemonic techniques workshops with students with SpLDs.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The procrastination significantly affects the performance of students with SpLDs. The individual method of study seems to be influenced by factors related to reading comprehension. The results showed that procrastination is part of reading self-esteem behaviors. Training with metacognitive skills exercises help control emotional and academic procrastination. The calculation of concentration of attention is a central issue in the training of metacognitive skills indicated by self-reports of them with which they assess the degree of concentration in certain lesson texts. Data from the factors that coexist in the individual study method and co-shape procrastination behaviors in reading comprehension in a student with dyslexia are presented below.

1st lesson: Farm Animal Diseases [i] with degree of difficulty in understanding [7 out of 10], where the individual method includes the [1] book, the [2]e-class, with the notes of the teaching professors, the [3] notes, handwritten or electronic of the students, the [4] telelectures, the [5] attendance with physical presence. Emotions are stated as disoriented, with high procrastination assessed by the students with SpLDs, [5 out of 5] and assessment of the degree of concentration in certain texts of the course [7 out of 10], in which it is examined for the first time with developmental questions. The student has done oral and written negotiation with the professor.

2nd lesson: Farm Animal Diseases [e] is examined in the stables. 3rd lesson: Nutrition Monogastric [i] with a degree of difficulty in comprehension [7 out of 10], where the individual method includes the [1] book, the [2]e-class, with the notes of the teaching professors, the [3] notes, handwritten or electronic of the students. The emotions are stated as disoriented, with great procrastination estimated by the SpLDs, [5 out of 5] because he does not attend classes because he works in catering and could not wake up in the morning. The assessment of the degree of concentration in certain texts of the course [7 out of 10], in which it is examined for the first time with development questions. She has done oral and written negotiation with one of the three professors for more time and for the opportunity to ask clarifying questions on difficult to understand topics.

4th lesson: Nutrition Monogastric [e] is examined in Computers. 5th lesson: Production of Aquatic Organisms [i] with a very high degree of difficulty in understanding [9 out of 10], where the atomic method includes the [1] book, the [2]e-class, with the notes of the teaching professors, the [3] notes, handwritten or electronic of the students. Emotions are stated as disoriented, with great procrastination estimated by the SpLDs, [5 out of 5] because he does not attend physical attendances because he works in catering and cannot wake up in the morning. The assessment of the degree of concentration in some texts of the course is only [3 out of 10], in the course it is examined for the first time with questions right wrong. It is noted that he has not made oral and written negotiations with the professor.

6th lesson: Production of Aquatic Organisms [e] does not know how it is examined. 7th lesson: Feed Technology [i] with medium degree of difficulty in comprehension [5 out of 10], where the individual method includes the [1] book, the [2]e-class, with the notes of the teaching professors, the [3] notes, handwritten or electronic of the students. Emotions are stated as disoriented, with procrastination assessed by the SpLDs, [3 out of 5] because they have only attended the course 5 times. The assessment of the degree of concentration in some course texts is [6 out of 10], in the course it is examined for the first time with development questions. It is noted that he has not made oral and written negotiations with the professor.

8th lesson: Feed Technology [e] is considered with growth questions. 9th lesson: Rural Sociology [i] with medium degree of difficulty in comprehension [5 out of 10], where the individual method includes the [1] book, the [2]e-class, with the notes of the teaching professors, the [3] notes, handwritten or electronic of the students, the [4] telelectures, the [5] attendance with physical presence. Emotions are stated as negative, with procrastination assessed by the SpLDs, [5 out of 5] because he has difficulty understanding the teacher's traditions. The assessment of the degree of concentration in some texts of the course is [5 out of 10], in the course it is examined for the first time with development questions. It is noted that he has not made oral and written negotiations with the professor.

10th lesson: Design and Organization of Livestock Units [i] with maximum degree of difficulty in understanding [10 out of 10], where the individual method includes the [1] book, the [2]e-class, with the notes of the teaching professors, the [3] notes, handwritten or electronic of the students, the [4] telelectures. Emotions are declared negative, he has missed many lessons, with great procrastination estimated by the SpLDs, [5 out of 5] he states that he was overwhelmed by the first lesson with what he heard in class, because he did not understand them. The assessment of the degree of concentration in some texts of the course is only [3 out of 10], in the course it is examined for the first time with questions right wrong. It is noted that he has not made oral and written negotiations with the professor.

11th lesson: E-commerce [i] with a low degree of difficulty in understanding [3 out of 10], where the individual method includes the [1]e-class, with the notes of the teaching professors, the [2] notes, handwritten or electronic of the students. Emotions are stated as positive, with procrastination assessed by the SpLDs, [3 out of 5] states "he had put us to work and I postponed it. I did it yesterday while the delivery is tonight." The assessment of the degree of concentration in some texts of the course is high [9 out of 10], in the course it is examined for the first time with questions right wrong. It is noted that he has made oral and written negotiations with the professor.

Lesson 12: E-Commerce [e] is examined with computer exercises.

The collective results for procrastination suggest consequences with reduced performance in both SpLDs [50%] and those without SpLDs [60%], who pay attention without having studied and understood the texts they do not understand and fail. Few [10%] on the last day or even immediately after the exam send emails that they had difficulties in their daily lives [work in restaurants, private lessons, illnesses, family issues] and were unable to study. Many [25%], although they have registered for courses and workshops,

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do not attend both lectures and exams.

CONCLUSION

The procrastination significantly affects the performance of students with SpLDs. The individual method of study seems to be influenced by factors related to reading comprehension. The results showed that procrastination is part of reading self-esteem behaviors. Training with metacognitive skills exercises help them to control emotional and academic procrastination applying the principles of Targeted Individual Structured Differentiated Integration Program for teaching students with Specific Learning Difficulties [TISDPfSpLDs] in the University. The calculation of concentration of attention is a central issue in the training of metacognitive skills indicated by self-reports of the students with SpLDs which they assess the degree of concentration in certain lesson texts using the educational interventions according the issues of Special Education and Training [SET]. Based on the results of this study, it can be concluded that qualitative research are new findings for the university' students with SpLDs in reading comprehension focus in the five topics. [1] The degree of difficulty in understanding includes the individual study method of reading comprehension texts from the book, the e-class, with the notes of the teaching professors, from the notes, handwritten or electronic of the University's students, from the telelectures, and the attendance with physical presence, from the results of identifying the procrastination into the individual study method of students with specific learning difficulties [SpLDs] in reading comprehension conclude in the five topics. [2] The high procrastination into the individual study method is stated with negative emotions or disoriented. [3] The assessment of the low degree of concentration in certain texts of the course connect with the SpLDs for reading comprehension. [4] The how many, unsuccess times which the course has be examined connect with the reading comprehension and the high procrastination [5] The procrastination is stated with the refusal to recognize their SpLDs and do oral and written negotiation with the professor. The proposals for the further education of metacognitive skills stem from the need to expand supportive interventions in Tertiary Education interactive and inclusive education [20] [29] [3]. Metacognitive skills training teaches all students to realize the consequences of low reading self-esteem [12] [9] [4] and to control perceptions stemming from interactive perceptual relationships with peers. In addition, the extension of this document based on the parameter of the minimum admission base is proposed to be examined in another research focusing on the criteria and motivations with which students chose to study at a certain University. In conclusion, this study could give rise to further discussion on academic procrastination and possible applications in the way universities organize their curriculum and in the way students with SpLDs communicate and interact with teachers. The grade of minimum basis for admission to universities is judged as the starting point to investigate what exactly has happened to the mental health [4] and the student enters with eight out of twenty degrees in a department of the University. For these reasons, it is necessary to create an autonomous supportive learning environment in universities, which will not overlook the factors that articulate the psyche of students with or without SpLDs, but will take care of and strengthen them.

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Table of acronyms

1. Specific learning difficulties SpLDs
2. Special Education and Training [SET]
3. Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder [ADHD]
4. Autism Spectrum Disorders [ASD]
4. Framework Curriculum of Special Education [FCSE]
5. Targeted Individual Structured Differentiated Integration Program for teaching students with Specific Learning Difficulties [TISDPfSpLDs].
6. Self-Determination Theory [SDT]

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